

SmartChat – An Intelligent Environment for Collaborative Discussions

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Abstract: Collaborative learning can be motivated via environments that provide communication, and areas for discussion. In such environments, both students and instructors need online support in order to produce useful interactions. In this paper we present SmartChat, an intelligent environment for collaborative discussions. It uses an argumentation model to organise users interactions and it classifies users in pre-defined stereotypes, based on their participation in the discussion. That classification helps the SmartChat's agent society to interfere in the discussion, in order to motivate users participation, and also recommend references or incentivate pair collaboration. SmartChat was developed in Java, using a knowledge base accessed through JEOPS. The initial tests have indicated promising results.

1. Introduction

Recent developments in communication technologies have favored the implementation of Computer Supported Collaborative Learning Environments (CSCLE) [1, 2] that take advantage from group interactions at a reasonable cost. In such environments, two or more participants build their knowledge together, through reflection, collaborative problem resolution, information exchange, and decision-making. In fact, the valorization of the interaction process (originated in the Socio-Constructivist Theory [3]) is quite common in current systems. This is done in order to improve the learning process.

However, in spite of the value ascribed to interactions in CSCLE, their content is not always taken into account. This fact can be corroborated when we observe the existing CSCLE. The majority of them provide tools for communication (e-mails, chats, and forums). However there are no mechanisms for the evaluation of the interaction contents. Such evaluation mechanisms could be of assistance in discovering both the problematic and points of interest of a given student or a group. Besides, this evaluation helps to single out the best students that could act as tutors to their peers. The lack of a mechanism to evaluate the interactions could prevent the users from discussing about a specific theme or collaborating among themselves.

Among the communication tools previously mentioned, we believe that the chat is one of the most effective. Since it is a synchronous tool, it is the one that mostly resembles the experiences students have in a conventional classroom. In this context, we developed SmartChat, an intelligent chat environment for the discussion of specific issues (preconfigured in an ontology [4]). SmartChat has two main components: the chat interface, and the reasoning mechanism. This mechanism consists of an agent society [5] that monitors and analyzes the users discussion, and intervenes in the chat trying to make the collaboration more productive. The prototype was developed in Java [6] and its reasoning mechanism uses a hybrid base of objects and rules, accessed by the inference motor JEOPS [7]. Preliminary tests yielded promising results.

The remainder of this document is structured as follow. Section 2 discusses existing chat environments. Section 3 presents SmartChat's architecture, argumentation model employed, and its user interface. Section 4 summarizes the tests performed and obtained results. Finally, section 5 discusses our conclusion and suggests future works.

2. Chat Environments

Chat Environments are synchronous communication tools, through which users can exchange ideas and collaborate with each other. In this section, we will analyze some chat environments considering the following criteria: (1) record of the interaction log; (2) technique employed in the interaction analysis; (3) goal of the interaction analysis; (4) way of intervening in the conversation; (5) provision of feedback for the teacher or the student; (6) use of an argumentation model; (7) interface usability.

Among the criteria above, we single out the use of argumentation models because we consider that they bring benefits to the chat environment. This is due to the fact that argumentation models have been frequently employed as a way of systematizing the communication patterns between the members of a group [8]. The use of argumentation models implies in classifying all the elements of the discussions into predefined model abstractions (e.g., argument, explanation, question, etc.), and link them through a set of predefined relationships. As a result, it is possible to capture the collective interaction memory for later storage and retrieval. This is the case, for instance, of Belvedere [9] and SISCO [10].

We have analysed three environments: The jXChat [11], Comet [12] and BetterBlether [13]. The results of this analysis, according to the defined criteria, can be found in Table 1. From the results listed in this table, we can see that, when a chat offers more resources to support teachers and/or students during the discussion, its interface becomes a hindrance to the user due to information overload. We have also observed that the system only provide feedback to the teacher, leaving the student without information about her/his performance in the discussion. Furthermore, even the systems that provide feedback, do so through reports or statistics generated from the interaction log, and only at the end of the discussion.

There is no feedback provided during the discussion, and none of the systems make use of the argumentation model. To structure the conversation, some systems use only sentence openers.

Environments Criteria	<i>jXChat</i>	<i>Comet</i>	<i>BetterBlether</i>
Record of the interaction log	Yes	Yes	Yes.
Technique employed in the interaction analysis	Compares input text with words stored in a Data Base.	Uses Hidden Markov Model.	No automated analysis is provided
Goal of the interactions analysis	To check whether the student's participation is related to the discussion subject.	To identify which students are sharing their knowledge.	No automated analysis is provided
Way of intervening in the conversation	Intervenes when authorized by the teacher. Sends emails to students and teachers to announce relevant events.	There are no intervention mechanisms	There are no intervention mechanisms
Feedback for the teacher or the student	Provides a report for the teacher, based on the dialogue log.	No feedback is provided.	Provides a statistical report for the teacher, based on the dialogue log..
Use of an argumentation model	No argumentation model is provided.	No argumentation model is provided.	No argumentation model is provided.
Interface usability	The user interface is fairly easy to use.	The user interface is not very easy to use. The screen is overloaded with information.	The user interface is not very easy to use. The screen is overloaded with information.

Table 1 - Comparative Analysis of Chat Environments

In the next section, we introduce SmartChart, an intelligent chat environment for collaborative discussions that offers solutions for some of the problems posed by the chats evaluated in this section.

3. SmartChat

Here, we present the SmartChat 's architecture, argumentation model, and interface. Its prototype was implemented using RMI (Remote Method Invocation) [6]. Its reasoning mechanism uses an agent society to monitor and analyze the interactions between the users, and to interact with them in the course of the conversation. It was developed in Java [6] and uses a hybrid knowledge base of rules and objects accessed by the JEOPS inference motor [7]. The domain ontology was implemented in XML [14]. An overview of the SmartChat architecture can be seen in Fig.1.

Fig. 1- SmartChat's Architecture

2.2 Environment Architecture

SmartChat's agent society consists of two intelligent agents: the Monitor and the Modeller Agents. The Monitor Agent is responsible for monitoring the chat and transmitting all the perceptions necessary for decision making (whether to interfere or not in conversation) to the Modeller Agent. The Monitor Agent was implemented as a thread and constantly monitors the messages sent to users. With each message sent, the Monitor uses a parser to uncover its context [15], using a domain ontology. Initially, the domain ontology employed deals with these subjects: Intelligent Agents, First-Order Logic, and Knowledge Representation according to Russel and Norvig [16].

Since the user sometimes does not use the argumentation model abstractions (e.g. Question, Argument, Explanation, or Maintenance) to categorize her/his message, SmartChat tries to infer a category. In order to do so, the Monitor Agent uses a predefined vocabulary of word categories (for example, question words such as : “what”, “why”, “when”, “how” etc). This agent is also responsible for generating the log of the interactions taking place in the environment and, for issuing different statistical reports for teachers and students at the end of the interaction. The teacher report presents general statistics about all the students, indicating the most discussed topic, the most and the less active students, and the topic that caused more conflicts. The student report presents her/his individual performance in relation to the group’s.

Fig. 2 - User Model Stereotypes

The Modeller Agent centralizes the main activities in the chat. It models the profile of the users logged-in and decides at what moment to interfere in the conversation. This agent was implemented as a thread and “wakes up” each time a group of ten messages arrives at the chat server. This agent communicates with the rule database generated by JEOPS [7] which is used to classify the user as one of the stereotypes (see Fig. 2) stored in the user model. The stereotypes are based on the idea that the users belong to homogeneous groups and describe their performance during the chat session [17]. In the context of this

work, the identification of the user with a category allows the Modeller to interfere in the discussion to perform one of the three following actions: (1) send support messages to the users (e.g. “Well done! You’ve got excellent explanations!” or “You are so laconic, wouldn’t you like to participate more?”) according to the stereotype s/he fits in; (2) suggest references related to the subject being discussed (e.g., “If you have doubts about this subject, then you should consult the X book”); and (3) name another chat user that may collaborate with the user having difficulties (e.g., “Look, maybe Joe can help you with your doubts. Why don’t you talk to him?”).

In motivating the student and striving to stimulate the collaboration between users, we try to make the interactions in SmartChat more effective and focused in the subject being discussed.

2.3 Argumentation Model

SmartChat uses a simplified argumentation model, based on the IBIS model [18], to structure the information contained in the interactions and to categorize the messages exchanged between students. The user that wishes to interact with the environment should select an abstraction from a predefined set (for example, Argument, Question, etc.), in order to provide explicit information about the intention of her/his messages. As a result, the environment uses previous semantic knowledge about the categories and the explicit relation between the messages to organize and infer information. The use of an argumentation model favours the resolution of conflicts and the understanding of problems, helping the participants to structure their ideas more clearly. Fig. 3 shows the argumentation model used by SmartChat. This model employs the following abstractions:

- *Maintenance* – used to keep a dialogue going; uses phrases that do not effectively contribute to the discussion (e.g. “Hi, how do you do?”, “Joe, are you there?”, or “My name is Anna, and yours?”);
- *Question* – is either a questioning about the topics being discussed, a request or a challenge (e.g. “What is an intelligent agent?”, “Could you give me a reference?” or “Are you sure about what you are saying?”);

- *Argument* – are observations that can lead to a debate. Generally, arguments are contributions or opinions (e.g: “I don’t agree with you in this point because I think that Deliberative Agents are more difficult to implement than are Cognitive Agents.”);
- *Explanation* – is a detailed answer to a question previously made. It can support or challenge an argument (e.g: “According to Russel and Norvig, an agent is a sistem capable of perceive through its sensors the stimuli coming from the environment of which it is part and react through its actuators”).

Fig. 3 - Argumentation Model used in SmartChat

2.4 User Interface

SmartChat is an easy to use system, where all text areas have associated hints. The system’s interface can be seen in Fig. 4.

To log on to the SmartChat server, the user must know either the server’s IP number (for example, 192.168.174.25) or the name of the machine (for example, machine1) where the server is installed, fill in the “Servidor” and “Nickname” fields and press the “Conectar” button. In the lower left corner of the screen, the system status (“on-line” or “off-line”) is exhibited, as well as the occurrence of some other problem (e.g. unavailable Internet connection).

Fig. 4 - SmartChat Interface

Once connected to the server, the user will receive a welcome message and, if desired, will also see the message log occurred prior to her/his connection. This can be done by clicking “Ver Histórico de Msgs”.

To send a message, the user must first select the argumentation model abstraction (e.g. TALK, EXPLAIN) by clicking on the combobox, named “Ação”. If an action is not selected, SmartChat will try to infer some abstraction suitable to the text of the message to be sent. Once an abstraction is chosen, the user must select the receiver of the message. This is done by clicking on the combobox “Para”, which contains the names of all logged on users. Lastly, the message content should be typed in the window “Mensagem” and the “Enviar” button should be pressed.

If the message to be sent is related to a previous message on the Message History area (named “Mensagens”), the user may point this out to the system by clicking on the previous message. After that, the message will appear in the “Mensagem de Referência” area, and the user may proceed to send her/his

new message the same way as explained before. This is done whenever the user wants to explicitly show the relationship between her/his message and the one belonging to the “Mensagens” area. For instance, the user might want to answer a previously asked question.

4. Tests and Results

An important step in the process of validating the chat was the execution of a test that aimed at checking: (1) if the users would be assigned adequate stereotypes; (2) the level of acceptance of the interferences from the Monitor Agent; (3) the correctness of the statistics produced, and (4) the environment usability.

Ten people were chosen to participate in this test. Participants should have basic knowledge about the issues dealt with by the domain ontology (e.g., Intelligent Agents, Knowledge Representation). They were asked to use SmartChat to discuss about Intelligent Agents.

During two hours of chat, the users could test all the functionalities of the environment and observe its weak and strong points. Firstly, it was observed that the system fulfilled its goals. The interaction analysis took place correctly, all users were classified according to the profile presented during the session, and received appropriate messages from the Monitor Agent informing about their situation.

However, some limitations could also be observed: the domain ontology needs to be extended, in order to acknowledge word variations used in the discussion (plurals, abbreviations, marks, synonyms); the log being recorded is confusing, giving users that wish to observe the interactions during the discussions a hard time. The users also suggested that the report generated at the end of the discussion should be improved to offer more information and statistics about the chat. All these observations were recorded and will be taken into account in the implementation of the next version of SmartChat.

5. Conclusions and Further Work

Effective collaborative interactions have been considered as a powerful and successful learning method. Students effectively learn in groups, where one encourages the other by asking, answering, reasoning,

explaining, justifying their opinions and reflecting about what is being discussed. The learning achieved through the dialogue between students is more effective than between student and teacher because in conversations between equals, the parts tend to feel more at ease to express their doubts and to justify and explain better their answers to each other. Thus, the interaction becomes the key element to understand the process of building knowledge and the role of each student in the process. The interaction analysis can produce resources for the system to support individual and group needs as well as to better evaluate their behavior, attitudes, knowledge level, and difficulties.

In this article, we presented SmartChat, a chat environment for collaborative discussing, that monitors online discussions, and interacts with the users to motivate them, to point references or to suggest the collaboration between two peers. SmartChat employs an argumentation model that is an extension of IBIS. The system's interface is simple and does not overload the user with large amounts of data, like other collaborative chats (described in section 2). The initial tests performed with SmartChat indicated users' satisfaction with the interface usability, good acceptance of the inferences and interventions performed by the SmartChat Agents, and the correctness of the classification of the users using the environment.

In the very near future, we will concentrate on extending the domain ontology to allow the recognition of more words, along with their spelling variations and synonyms (for example, Artificial Intelligence, AI). After that, we intend to implement an on-line feedback area to inform the students about their performance in relation to the group. We also intend to enrich the student and teacher reports with more relevant information, such as individual statistics for each user compared to the group, as well as to improve the organization of the interaction log.

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